

Preparations and Physico-chemical Studies of Some Metal Complexes of Thiophene Derivatives

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Preparations of 2-Thenylamine and 5-methylthiophene-2-aldoxime complexes with chlorides of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pd(II) are described. Elemental analyses are made and stoichiometric formulae are assigned. I.R. absorption frequencies are reported for N-H (stretching and bending) vibrations for amine complexes; and O-H (stretching and deformation), C=N (conjugated) and N-O vibrations for oxime complexes. All the complexes are found to be nonelectrolytes.

STUDIES on complex equilibria involving thiophene-2-carboxylic acid and its tetrahydroderivative several amino- and amido-derivatives of thiophene with various metal ions have been described by A. K. Chaudhury *et al.*^{1,2}. In the present paper syntheses of several complexes of MCl_2 ($M = Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)$ and $Pd(II)$) with 2-thenylamine and 5-methylthiophene-2-aldoxime, their elemental analysis, conductance measurements and i.r. spectral studies will be described. Gonick *et al.*³ investigated the 2-thenylamine complexes of divalent metal ions in aqueous solutions. Coakley *et al.*⁴ prepared thiophene-2-aldoxime complexes with chlorides of $Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)$ and $Pd(II)$.

Experimental

Reagents: Thiophene (B. D. H., Poole, England) was used as received. Absolute alcohol was allowed to stand over CaO for several days and then distilled. All other reagents including anhydrous $ZnCl_2$ and $CuCl_2$ were of A. R. or G. R. grade. Anhydrous $NiCl_2$ (yellow)^{5a} and $CoCl_2$ (blue)^{5b} were obtained by heating their hydrates at 120-140° in air-oven.

Syntheses of ligands :

2-Thenylamine (2-TA): It was prepared by following the method due to H. D. Hartough⁶.

5-Methyl-thiophene-2-aldoxime (5-Me-T-2-OXM): It was prepared from 5-methyl-thiophene-2-aldehyde and NH_2OH . HCl as was described by Tandon *et al.*⁷ in the preparation of thiophene-2-aldoxime.

Preparation of Complexes :

The complexes were prepared by dissolving the anhydrous metal chlorides and the ligands separately in anhydrous ethanol. They are allowed to react

in stoichiometric proportions, keeping always the ligand in slight excess. For palladium complexes, lithium chloropalladate solution in 1-butanol was used which was prepared by the method of Busch *et al.*⁸. 2-Thenylamine complexes were obtained directly. Refluxing was necessary only in a few cases. For 5-methylthiophene aldoxime complexes refluxing for 40-50 minutes were necessary. The palladium complex were well crystalline and they were recrystallised. Due to solubility difficulties most of the other complexes could not be recrystallised. The complexes were decomposed in a mixtures of nitric acid and sulphuric acid and the metals were estimated by standard methods. Chloride was determined as $AgCl$, Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldhal method⁹. Electrical conductance measurements were done with an Industrial Instruments Model RE-16B2 Conductivity Bridge. All measurements were made around 30° at a frequency 50 c.p.s with a cell of cell constant 1.42 cm^{-1} . Nitrobenzene was used as solvent. The i.r. spectra in KBr pellets were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 457 Spectrophotometer in the region $4000-250\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data and the molar conductances of $0.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ solution of the complexes in nitrobenzene at 30° are given in Table 1. Infrared absorption frequencies are given in Table 2 and 3.

Low values of molar conductances indicate nonelectrolytic nature of the complexes. The compounds as already stated are not easily recrystallisable and they hardly dissolve in any solvent. So their solution spectra in the visible region are not studied. From the above evidences it is clear that chloride is in the coordination zone and in possibly most cases the ligand acts as monodentate. It is almost certain therefore that the Cu, Pd and Ni compounds are square planar and Zn and Cd compounds are tetrahedral.

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TABLE—1 ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF COMPLEXES OF 2-TA AND 5-ME-T-2-OXM(L).

Complex	Color	Molar conductance		Analysis				
		cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	Metal	Found % Cl	N	Metal	Required % Cl	N
CuCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	Yellow	1.76	25.4	27.90	5.40	26.60	28.60	5.60
CuCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	Green	3.22	17.7	19.20	8.00	17.60	19.60	7.80
PdCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	Golden yellow	1.85	27.01	17.01	6.58	26.43	17.57	6.93
NiCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	Green	2.37	15.95	19.72	7.68	16.51	19.95	7.87
ZnCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	White	5.86	18.90	20.21	8.42	18.05	19.57	7.73
CdCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	White	1.71	26.85	17.05	6.75	27.27	17.32	6.84
CoCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	Blue	2.52	15.65	19.75	7.63	16.57	19.93	7.87
CuCl ₂ L ₂	Reddish-brown	8.66	14.95	17.09	6.50	15.26	17.02	6.72
(L=5-MeT-2-OXM)								
PdCl ₂ L ₂	Yellow	5.37	23.08	14.85	5.84	23.21	15.43	6.09
CoCl ₂ L ₂	Red	6.25	14.02	16.58	5.54	14.32	17.32	6.80
CdCl ₂ L ₂	White	Insoluble in Ph.NO ₂	23.85	15.20	5.90	24.15	15.24	6.01
NiCl ₂ L ₂	Green	5.06	14.10	16.85	6.43	14.27	17.23	6.80

TABLE—2 INFRA-RED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹) OF 2-TA, 2-TA.HCl AND SOME COMPLEXES FORMED FROM 2-TA IN KBr DISCS.

Compound	N-H Bending frequency (cm ⁻¹)		N-H Stretching frequency (cm ⁻¹)	
2-TA	1640s	1550m	3426	3310
2-TA.HCl	1500s		3000s	
CuCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	1578w	1530w	3200s	3188sh
CuCl ₂ .(2-TA)	1600s		3230m	
PdCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	1580m		3250s	
ZnCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	1560s	1548sh	3264s	
CdCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	1600m		3244s	3300s
CoCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	1620s		3260m	3320m
NiCl ₂ .2(2-TA)	1625s		3330w	3260w

Sh=Shoulder, m=medium
S=strong, w=weak

TABLE—3 PRINCIPAL I.R. ABSORPTION BANDS FOR 5-METHYL-THIOPHENE-2-ALDOXIME AND SOME COMPLEXES OF IT IN KBr DISCS (FREQUENCY IN CM⁻¹)

5-Me-T-2 OXM(L)	CuCl ₂ L ₂	NiCl ₂ L ₂	CoCl ₂ L ₂	CdCl ₂ L ₂	PdCl ₂ L ₂	Possible Assignment
3140w	3190s	3220s	3240s	3465m	3160s	O-H stretch
1632m	1650s	1644w	1642m	3360w		
1465m	1454s	1453s	1452s	1640s	1650s	O-H deformation
940w	982s	948m	949s	1449m	1455s	C=N stretch
	590s	565w	600s	955w	998s	N=O stretch
	264w	-	300w	585m	595m	(M-N) stretch
					312w	(M-Cl) stretch

sh = shoulder, m = medium, s = strong, w = weak.

I.R. Spectra of Complexes :

Selected I-R data and assignments are set out in Tables 2 and 3. The O-H stretching frequency (at 3140 cm⁻¹) for the oxime is lowered^{4,10} a great deal from 3700-3560 cm⁻¹ which is usual for unbounded O-H. On complex formation it is shifted to higher frequency¹¹. We wish to note that the absorption around 1650-1632 cm⁻¹ (Table 3) was originally assigned to C = N stretch⁴. But since this frequency is shifted to higher values in going from ligand to complex it is more likely that this band is due to O-H deformation¹¹. We assign the band around 1465-1455 cm⁻¹ to C = N stretch.

Now we find the expected lowering of frequency in going from ligand to complex. This is in line with reported works on oxime systems¹²⁻¹⁶.

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